

CONCEPTUALIZATION OF CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

The theoretical-audiovisual essay *Conceptualization of Change* is a 12-minute film that reflects on the complexities of the signifier change, and its multitudes of meanings. Originating from a 2020 colloquium on “Mediating Change”, the essay still includes references to this first exchange of thoughts, through the use of an imaginary seminar room. The main part of the film is structured through five dimensions of change: “Normativity”, “Scale and Intensity”, “Focus/interconnectivity”, “Control” and “Time”. The textual reflection in each of these chapters is combined with, and enhanced by, impressionistic and poetic images that were filmed in Prague, intertwined with archive material mostly related to the Czechoslovak Velvet Revolution of 1989 and the Russian invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968.

Keywords: Change; Constructionism; Signification; Audiovisual essay; Fluidity; Conflict.

Conceptualization of Change is a short 12-minute theoretical audiovisual essay that provides a reflection on the signifier change. Through five dimensions—five chapters, namely “Normativity”, “Scale and Intensity”, “Focus/interconnectivity”, “Control” and “Time”—the essay unpacks the complexities of change, and its diversity of meanings and theoretical points of view. Analytically and methodologically, the film uses a post-structuralist paradigm (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985; Laclau, 2000; Carpentier, 2017), discursively elaborating how the elements of the signifier change have been socially constructed and mediated (Doudaki et al. 2022a; 2022b), and contemplating about the hegemonic and counter-hegemonic forces within each of the 5 dimensions.

Theoretically and conceptually, the audiovisual essay's starting point is a reflection about the contributions at the “Mediating Change” Colloquium that took place in Prague (Czech Republic) on the 20th and 21st November 2020. The diversity of these contributions was then enriched by a series of literature review cycles, using a multidisciplinary approach, resulting in a broad reflection about the nature of change, and how it is conceptualized.

The first chapter (“Normativity”) captures a general prehension of change, either as a move towards a particular utopia, where the present is disputed and the future is aimed to be reconfigured (see, e.g., Tufte, 2017; Servaes, 2018), or as a shift towards a dystopia, articulating the new as a threat that requires care (in order to be avoided) and provokes anxiety (Claeys, 2017). These normative positions consequently create space within which societal struggles over the future can take place.

The “Scale and Intensity” chapter reflects on how change can have micro or macro forms and impacts, on a variety of societal levels and groups. Changes can range from modifications in everyday life (which might be more fundamental than perceived at first sight, see de Certeau, 1984; Shove, et al., 2012), to full-scale political revolutions (Thompson, 1997) These changes can be visible or remain invisible. In this dimension, the questions are also about which particular shifts in society (or nature) are sufficiently relevant in order to be characterized as change.

The “Focus” chapter deals with the autonomy of change, and its relationship to stability and continuity. Sometimes change is defined in isolation of the structural stabilities that allow for change to take place, while in other cases the mutual dependency of change and stability is acknowledged (see March, 1996; Herrfahrdt-Pähle & Pahl-Wostl, 2012). Here, change and stability/continuity are seen to co-exist and overlap, as not everything is changing all the time, and all change integrates some degree of stability/continuity, and vice-versa.

The fourth chapter (“Control”) deals with how change can be controlled and how it is controlling. Change can be organized and coordinated by humans, but in many other cases, humans only have a limited ability to affect change, as, for instance, natural phenomena and the power of nature demonstrate (Latour, 2017).

Finally, the “Time” chapter refers to the different conceptions of change over time, which can be perceived as either as an outcome, articulated with a specific event or date, or as a process within a longer period where societal structures are changing (Braudel, 1969; de Certeau, 1992; Schatzki, 2010). These approaches demonstrate the existence of different time-frames when trying to understand change.

Format-wise, the audiovisual essay includes a combination of observatory poetic shots, filmed in Prague, intertwined with archive material mostly related to the Czechoslovak Velvet Revolution of 1989 and the Russian invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968. Together, they refer to the interconnection of experienced reality, societal fluidity and the workings of (counter) hegemonies.

“How can we define change?”, the opening sentence of the essay, evokes the main topic of “Conceptualization of Change”, and is followed by a one-minute prologue in an imaginary seminar room, filled with the voices of scientists—discussing the variety of meanings of change—from the “Mediating Change” colloquium. Then, a more general theoretical discussion on change unfolds, which is structured into the five chapters (or dimensions of change).

Each dimension is introduced in the imaginary seminar room. As the theoretical elaboration of each dimension starts, viewers move out of the seminar room, and enter the outside world, to experience the theoretical reflection on everyday realities or their residua. Eventually, the essay returns to the seminar room, to listen to the final conclusion of the scientists in the epilogue. Although by then, viewers will have experienced a detailed elaboration of the five dimensions of change, to help to understand change as a concept that is relative and not pre-given. At the same time, in the epilogue, we are reminded how difficult it is to produce an all-encompassing definition of change.

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